

A STUDY FOR THE MOISTURE CONTENT OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE WITH HYGROTHERMAL CYCLING

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ABSTRACT—Resin matrix composite materials have been gaining increasingly wide use in commercial, military and space applications because of the excellent strength to weight ratio characteristics. There is a concern that the mechanical properties of such materials may suffer from the environmental factors such as, moisture and temperature. In order to utilize the full potential of composite materials for the composite elements and structures applications, the moisture content of composite material has to be well defined in advance.

Due to the wide usage of composite material, the material operation environments are usually various and transient. The Fick law was used for the moisture content model analysis under transient environment in this research. An environmental chamber has been designed and constructed to simulate cyclic environmental conditions. The moisture weight gain of IM6/3501-6 composite specimens under 12 hours “on-off” hygrothermal cyclic were measured; experimental data was compared to the numerical results for the numerical model evaluation. Using the real temperature and humidity histories as the transient boundary conditions, good correlations between experimental and numerical data were obtained. An evaluation for the transverse edge effect of composite laminate moisture weight gain was also included in this paper.

KEYWORDS: composite materials, moisture content, hygrothermal cycling, epoxy resins, edge effect

INTRODUCTION

The progress of manufacturing processes and the energy efficiency requirement have made smaller, lighter, thinner products the goal of many industries. The weight decrease has become the major subject of product design; for example, in aeronautical industry, the use of light-weighted material and the control of its property are one of the critical factors for the structure design of a space carrier. Because of its superior strength to weight ratio etc, composite has been largely used in civil, aeronautical, automobile, marine or even high tech industries. Since composite is used in many area, from aeronautical industry to marine industry even in electronic industry has its application, the applications of composite is diversified, from related studies and experiences, composite is very sensitive to environment temperature and moisture, especially, when operated under high temperature and high humidity.

In recent year, there are many studies related to the research of the composite material moisture content. Most of the study concentrated on the relation between composite material moisture content and exposure time under static environment. Little is mentioned on the moisture content of composite material under transient environment. Fick law can be used to analyze moisture diffusion problems. Jost[1] used Fickian process, assuming constant diffusivity with the initial and boundary condition, derived a feasible 1-D solution. In general, material's moisture diffusivity is related to material itself, material inner moisture content, stress and temperature. According to Augle and Traboccos[2] and Crank and Parks[3], composite moisture diffusivity can be obtained experimentally by assuming it is not affected by moisture content and fiber moisture diffusivity is much small than epoxy moisture diffusivity. Shen and Springer[4], using the same characteristic and thru epoxy moisture diffusivity

and fiber volume fraction to estimate composite moisture diffusivity, then derived an experimental equation to estimate the saturated moisture content of composite. Also, Loos and Springer [5] assumed moisture diffusivity is function of temperature, derived an experimental equation stated that composite moisture diffusivity and absolute temperature have an exponential relationship.

Hofer et al.[6], Kim and Whitney[7], Shen and Springer[8], Browning[9], and DeIasi and Whiteside[10] have done studies on graphite fiber/epoxy material property and strength with the effect of temperature and moisture content. According to their report, temperature and moisture content have considerable effects on the composite properties and strength, especially to 90° laminates. The reason is that material property of 90° laminate is determined by epoxy properties, and the epoxy is very sensitive to environment, such as temperature and moisture content.

For the further study of the hygrothermal effect, most researchers used moisture content to describe the hygrothermal effect on the composite material properties. How to accurately control composite moisture content and estimate the moisture content under long-term exposure have become the subjects of the composite properties research. As we mentioned, the applications environment for composite is varied. Under these environment, absorption and desorption of moisture occur inside the material interactively and cause the hygrothermal cycling effect. The investigation of long term hygrothermal cycling effect to the moisture content is not seen a lot. From the fundamental research point of view, it is necessary to have further study. The moisture weight gain of IM6/3501 composite specimens under 12 hours “on-off” hygrothermal cyclic were measured; experimental data was compared to the numerical results for the numerical model evaluation in this research.

THEORY AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The diffusion of moisture in a solid is basically the same as that of heat. This was recognized by Fick (1885) following the work of Fourier in heat conduction [11]. The 1-D moisture diffusion equation can be expressed as the following:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_m \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Where D_m is moisture diffusivity, and has the unit of length squared over time. C is moisture concentration. According to Shen, Springer [4] and Loos, Springer [5], it is a reasonable assumption to use Fick diffusion theory to analyze graphite/epoxy composite moisture content using fixed boundary conditions. Also, According to Augle and Trabocco [2], moisture content has little effects on these coefficients. Assuming moisture diffusivity D_m and material inner temperature are constant and therefore eqn. (1) can be rewritten as:

$$D_m \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

Assume there is a plate with thickness h , as shown in Fig. 1. Its initial and boundary conditions are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} T &= T_i, C = C_i ; 0 \leq x \leq h, t \leq 0 \\ T &= T_a, C = C_a ; x = 0 \text{ or } x = h, t \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Jost [1] solved eqn. (2) using above conditions, he found:

$$\frac{C - C_i}{C_m - C_i} = 1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2j+1} \sin\left[\frac{\pi(2j+1)x}{h}\right] \exp\left[\frac{-\pi^2(2j+1)^2 D_m t}{h^2}\right] \quad (3)$$

Where C_m is moisture concentration at the surface, C_i is material initial moisture concentration. In most applications, material inner moisture content is expressed as the percent moisture content, by integrating eqn.(3) with respect to h , eqn.(3) becomes:

$$\frac{M_t - M_i}{M_m - M_i} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2j+1)^2} \exp\left[-\frac{\pi^2(2j+1)^2 D_m t}{h^2}\right] \quad (4)$$

where

$$M_t = \frac{\text{wet plate weight} - \text{dry plate weight}}{\text{dry plate weight}} \times 100 = \frac{W_t - W_d}{W_d} \times 100$$

$$M_i = \frac{\text{initial plate weight} - \text{dry plate weight}}{\text{dry plate weight}} \times 100 = \frac{W_i - W_d}{W_d} \times 100$$

$$M_m = \frac{\text{saturated wet plate weight} - \text{dry plate weight}}{\text{dry plate weight}} \times 100 = \frac{W_m - W_d}{W_d} \times 100$$

and $W_t = W_d + m_t g$; $W_i = W_d + m_i g$; $W_m = W_d + m_m g$, m_t is the mass of wet plate moisture, m_i is the mass of initial plate moisture and m_m is the mass of saturated wet plate moisture.

To solve eqn.(4), it is necessary to first solve composite moisture diffusivity D_m and its percent saturated moisture content M_m . Related methods are stated below:

I. Moisture Diffusivity, D_m

D_m can be obtained from the measured curve of composite moisture absorption rate or moisture desorption rate. The related method was done by Crank and Park [3]. For example, Fig.2 shows material percent moisture content M_t vs. \sqrt{t} ; the initial linear portion of the curve is consistent with Boltzman's solution for diffusion (1894). It's relationship is

$$\frac{M_t}{M_m} = \frac{4}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{t D_m}{h^2}} \quad (5)$$

The moisture c

ressed as:

$$D_m = \pi \left(\frac{h^2}{4 M_m} \right) \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

For the temperature-dependent only moisture diffusivity, D_m can be obtained using Loos and Springers' [5] experimental equation; Assuming the fiber moisture diffusivity D_f much smaller than D_m , D_m can be estimated thru epoxy moisture diffusivity D_r . Shen and Springer [4] suggested related calculation.

II. Maximum Moisture Content, M_m

The effect of temperature and relative humidity to the composite percent moisture content M_m can be

estimated using Shen and Springers' [4] empirical form:

$$M_m = a(\phi)^b \tag{7}$$

where ϕ is relative humidity, a and b are material constant. A summary of the a and b values, is given in Table 1.

Table 1. The a and b of composite and epoxy under wet atmosphere

Material	a	b
T300/1034	0.0170 [5]	1.00 [5]
AS/3501-5	0.0190 [5]	1.00 [5]
	0.0160 [12]	1.10 [12]
T300/5208	0.0150 [5]	1.00 [5]
	0.0155 [13]	1.00 [13]
3501-5*	0.0600 [12]	1.22 [12]
5208*	0.0590 [14]	1.00 [14]
	0.0660 [15]	1.28 [15]

Springer[16] used cyclic diffusion prob

*:pure epoxy

ite moisture used cyclic

manner to simulate actual cyclic variation, see Fig. 3. The numerical results obtained from Fick law with transient boundary conditions still needed to be verified by the experimental data, especially for the estimation of the composite moisture content under hygrothermal cyclic variation. In this study, we choose IM6/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite as our study object, since it's been largely used by the industry. We used eqn. (4) to estimate composite moisture content and then compared these value with measured value, to justify the accountability of this analytical procedure.

ENVIROMENTAL CHAMBER

To perform the related experiments, we designed a 54cm×36cm×22cm environmental chamber to fulfill the need for the hygrothermal requirement. The design diagram and the finished chamber are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5 respectively, this simulation chamber is a rectangular metal box and made out of Aluminum alloy. The entrie chamber is covered with insulation forms for the thermal insulation. A fan is installed inside the box to make sure temperature and humidity can reach desired value and uniform distributed through out the whole box quickly. A flow guliding plate is installed along the longitudinal center line to stabilize the air flow. Curved plates are installed at four corners to prevent the turbulance from happening. Heat source is provided by heaters. To increase the humidity, a flat pan with water and wick(fiber) hanger over it were used. Since the heat source is inside the box, for safety concern, a set of temperature control circuit (including solid state relay SSR and thermocouple) is installed to monitor the heater temperature and prevent it from over heating. The inside temperature is controlled by adjusting fan motor speed and temperature controller (including mechanical relay, thermocouple). Humidity is controlled by flat pan water level. Since this study required a continuous long-term measurement under the influence of high temperature and humidity, the accountability of testing apparatus and the requirement of the environment must be observed strictly.

Fig. 3 Schematic for variation boundary conditions of temperature and moisture

Fig. 4 Schemat

specimens

Wick

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Heaters

In this paper, the hygrothermal cycling used for the numerical and experimental analysis is as close to the actual operating condition as possible. To avoid the difficulty that may occur in the environmental simulation during the experiment, this study used 12 hours repeated cyclic (variation) environment to do the analysis. As see in Fig. 3, one hygrothermal cycle consist of two part: first is to put specimen in high-temperature, high-humidity environmental chamber for 12 hours, then open the chamber, let the specimen to stay in the room condition for another 12 hours. Continue on the cycle until the experiment is finished. Test material used is graphit/epoxy composite IM6/3501. For the stacking sequence and laminate thickness, see Table 2. Two set of specimens, IM6-3 and IM6a-1, were used in the test and the specimen size is 1in(25.4mm)×1in(25.4mm). To compare the experimental results with 1-D numerical solution, the sides of the specimens were sealed with lead tape¹. In this study, we have finished two tests with two different hygrothermal conditions. The hygrothermal condition used for the first test is 90°F(32.2°C), 98%RH. Fig. 6 recorded the environment variation during the test duration. The temperature variation is not significant due to the laboratory air control and the weather pattern is similar to that of from Summer to Winter. The hygrothermal condition used for the second test is 120°F(48.9), 98%RH. Fig. 7 recorded the environment variation during the testing period. The weather pattern is similar to that of from Winter to Summer.

Firstly, we used experimental results to get composite parameter to be used for the numerical analysis.

¹ The specimens IM6a-1 with one side without sealed are used to evaluate the transverse edge effect on the percent moisture content.

Among them, moisture diffusivity D_m can be obtained thru experimental methods using eqn. (6) and eqn. (7); it is done by using experiemntal data to get composite percent moisture content M_f vs \sqrt{t} curve and then use linear regression to get the slope of the linear part of the curve. Composite material saturated percent moisture content M_m can be obtained using eqn. (7). Since a and b is not available in any literature, their values, 0.0204 and 1.000 respectively, were estimated using data in Table 1. Relative humidity is the average value during the experimental process². The specimen thickness h are shown at Table2. The calculated value of D_m for IM6a-1 and IM6-3 are 3.292×10^{-8} mm²/sec and 1.279×10^{-7} mm²/sec respectively. Sih et al. [17] suggested that regular Graphite/epoxy composite humidity diffusivity is in the order of 10^{-7} . Compared to this value, these calculated data are considered reasonable and acceptable.

Table 2. Specimen set, material, thickness and stacking sequence

Specimen Set	Materials	Stacking Sequence	Thickness (mm)
IM6a-1	IM6/3501-6	[45/90/-45/0 ₃ /±45/0 ₃ /±45] _S	3.89
IM6-3	IM6/3501-6	[45/90/-45/0 ₃ /±45/0 ₃ /±45] _S	4.9

note IM6-3 specimen consists of the stacking of pre-preg IM6/3501-6 grade 190 tape; average thickness is 0.0074" (0.0188mm). IM6a-1 specimen is the stacking of pre-preg IM6/3501-6 grade 100 tape; the average thickness is 0.0059" (0.0150 mm). Both specimens have the same fiber volume fraction.

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definition of eqn. (5). In this equation, M_t is a measured value, M_m can be obtained from eqn. (7) and in order to simplify the estimation procedure, we assume specimen initial percent moisture content M_i is 0%. The numerical solution for percent moisture content can be obtained using eqn. (5) and the D_m value obtained from the experiment.

Both experimental data and numerical solution were organized and shown at Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. Fig. 8 showed the result of IM6a-1, the maximum variation of experimental value between two specimen, 2.5%, is acceptable. If compared this data to the numerical solution, the measured value is larger than numerical data by 20%. The reason for this different is one side of the speimen was not sealed that caused extra moisture weight gain for the speimen. Nevertheless, the curve trend of the experimental data and nuimerical solution are similary. Fig. 9 showed the result of IM6-3, the maximum variation of experimental value between two specimen, only 1.7%, is acceptable. The experimental data and numerical solution are very close, also the curve trend is the same. After the same time duration, a higher temperature condition gave a higher moisture percent content, as shown in Fig.9. From the above discussion, we concluded that composite 1-D moisture diffusivity numerical model derived using Fick law is very accurate when applied this to composite moisture content under hygrothermal cyclic environment.

² The room humidity and the chamber simulated humidity included.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this paper, we study the comparison between the numerical solution and experimental data of moisture content of IM6/3501-6 composite with hygrothermal cycling. The following are our conclusions and suggestions:

1. Composite 1-D moisture diffusivity numerical model derived using Fick law is very accurate when applying to estimate composite moisture content under hygrothermal cyclic environment.
2. Moisture content of composite is largely affected by side effect. This is confirmed in this study.
3. Using average relative humidity can simplify the analytical procedure for composite saturated percent moisture content.
4. Moisture diffusivity D_m was obtained from experimental data, this improved the numerical solution accuracy.
5. In numerical analysis, data used for variation, cyclic boundary condition calculation was obtained from experimental data and it is time-consuming, has to be simplified with an automatic environmental data acquisition system.

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